

Species behaviour affects recommended expose times of artificial substrates to sample benthic dinoflagellates

Harmful algal blooms caused by benthic microalgae (Benthic HABs) are far less studied than those caused by planktonic species. However, in recent years, the study of potentially harmful benthic dinoflagellates has garnered significant interest among HAB researchers [1]. In the southern Caribbean, notable observations include occurrence and persistence of benthic dinoflagellates belonging to the genera *Gambierdiscus*, *Prorocentrum* and *Ostreopsis*, alongside a long history of harmful events attributed to their presence [2, 3]. Species of *Gambierdiscus* are associated with the production of ciguatoxins and maitotoxins; benthic *Prorocentrum* species with okadaic acid and *Ostreopsis* species with palytoxins, ovatoxins, maccarenotoxins, ostreocins and other toxins that accumulate in shellfish and fish. These toxins can pose risks to public health and adversely impact economic activities such as tourism, fishing, and aquaculture.

The complex life styles of benthic dinoflagellates render their study somewhat difficult. While they are generally found in shallow waters and occasionally in the water column, these benthic microalgae primarily live in association with different types of substrates, such as macroalgae, seagrass, corals, rocks, and sediments [4].

Methods for quantifying benthic dinoflagellate populations face several limitations. Approaches based on natural substrates such as macrophytes (macroalgae and marine phanerogams) [5] must account for the morphological diversity and spatial and temporal variability of these substrates. Such variability complicates methodological standardization, hindering comparisons between studies. To overcome these challenges, artificial substrates have been increasingly employed [6]. Results are typically expressed as the number of cells per unit area, rather than per substrate weight, making quantitative comparisons across studies more practical and independent of natural substrate availability.

Artificial substrates offer several advantages. Unlike some natural macrophytes, they do not exude substances that attract or repel benthic dinoflagellates. Moreover, artificial substrates are less affected by grazing due to their non-palatability [7]. In addition to simplifying the estimation of benthic microalgal abundance, artificial substrates enable experimental manipulation to investigate the dynamics of substrate colonization. This can be achieved by varying exposure times and spatial arrangements. To minimize the effects of biotic processes such as competition and predation, short exposure times, not exceeding 24 hours, are generally recommended. However, given the diversity of life-cycle traits among benthic dinoflagellate species, optimal exposure times may vary depending on the target species and environmental conditions. This study presents findings (as part of a doctoral thesis) from experiments conducted to determine the appropriate exposure times of artificial substrates for representative species of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Prorocentrum* in the coastal waters of the southern Caribbean [8]. To evaluate the attachment and maintenance behaviour of dinoflagellates across different climatic periods (dry, transitional, and rainy seasons), artificial substrates made of fiberglass mesh (Fig. 1) were deployed in two bays within Tayrona

Fig. 1. Structure of the artificial fiberglass mesh substrates used to sample benthic microalgae (modified from [7]).

National Natural Park, Colombia. Population abundance was monitored after 24, 72, and 144 hours of exposure over six consecutive days. The assays revealed behavioural differences between *Gambierdiscus* sp. and *Prorocentrum* cf. *lima*. For *Gambierdiscus* sp. no significant changes in population abundance were observed between substrates exposed for 24, 72, and 144 hours, indicating that this species does not show a sustained increase or decrease in abundance with longer exposure times. Abundance estimates ranged from absent to 2,601 cells per 100 cm². These findings align with Nakahara et al. [9], who reported that *Gambierdiscus* cells do not attach permanently to substrates but detach in response to disturbances. Similarly, Parsons et al. [10] described *Gambierdiscus* as a non-obligate epiphyte, capable of both attachment and detachment over time.

In contrast, *Prorocentrum* cf. *lima* exhibited increases in average daily abundances during the dry season, with maximal densities of up to 118,931 cells per 100 cm² observed on substrates exposed for 72 and 144 hours (Fig. 2). This species demonstrated a stronger association with substrates, indicating longer attachment times. Consequently, using prolonged exposure times (>24 hours) may introduce biases in population assessments for *Prorocentrum*.

The study highlights the need to tailor substrate exposure times to the specific behaviours and habitat conditions of the target species. For *Gambierdiscus* sp., substrates can be exposed for 24 to 144 hours without significant changes in population abundance, whereas for *Prorocentrum* cf. *lima*, shorter exposure times (<24 hours) are advisable to avoid overestimating population densities.

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Fig. 2. Average abundance (cells per 100 cm⁻²) and standard deviation of *Gambierdiscus* sp. and *Prorocentrum* cf. *lima*, in fiberglass meshes exposed for 24 h, 72 h, and 144 h. The orange line represents the data obtained for each exposure period, while the black dots indicate the average abundance recorded during 24 h of exposure on the same day as the meshes exposed for the longer periods.

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